

The Canonical Equations of Curvature Spikes – The 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying Lorentz manifold with arbitrary variation that vanish into matter, it is possible to construct a new version of the canonical equation of motion. The new formation will be analyzed both for Fermions in which require the arbitrary variations to vanish, and for Bosons in which we do not, as they can not vanish due to being related to the prime numbers as was proven by the primordial coupling series.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1); (24 + (3)) + 3; (120 + (3)) + 5; (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it on the fine structure constant:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

In the 8T thesis, we have derived the fermions to by describe by the arbitrary amount of variations on the main equation, given by the term in (1.48):

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \partial g' = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor M:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Suppose we would like to present a simple way to create an analog for the canonical equations of motion, presented by Hamilton. How can we do it in a simple way on a varying Lorentz manifold, with four chained terms in the differential equation? This is an interesting question, and the real answer is one does not know. However, here is an educated guess. The idea is to use the terms in equations (1.48) and (1.49) to derive something fundamental about the momenta of Fermions and Bosons. Suppose we replace the known variable of Hamilton by:

$$\partial q_i \rightarrow \partial g_i$$

And we know from the equivalence principle that

$$\partial g_i = \partial g'_i$$

We can present the canonical equation of curvature spikes, if one intuition is correct:

$$\dot{p}_i = \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial g_i}$$

In addition, since we know it vanish into zero, we cannot present it as being in the denominator. We can than represent the canonical equation of curvature spikes for Fermions:

$$\partial g_i = \frac{\partial \ell}{\dot{p}_i} = 0 \quad (1.7)$$

And since we can derive the beautiful result, which comes to an agreement with previous results of the 8T, fermions momenta will vanish to zero. That is another way to state that they will accelerate toward one another. Therefore, configurations of Fermions must appear stationary, similar to Quark Triplets in Hadrons for example. Notice that the emphasis is not on constant rate but rather on the momenta of arbitrary variation set.

We can do the exact same thing for Bosons, since we know that they are isomorphic to prime numbers that cannot vanish into matter, the canonical equation of curvature spikes for Bosons is the following:

$$\partial g_i = \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial p_i} > 0 \quad (1.71)$$

Meaning that the Bosonic configuration must have some net momenta, we cannot find a Boson at rest. That is in agreement with the 8T ideas. Fermions have opposite signs, demands by stationary Lorentz manifold. Bosons are all positive summations, net curvature on the metric tensor isomorphic to prime numbers, they cannot cancel one another as Fermions do. That is similar to the idea construction in that led to the 8T commutator for fermions, plus, and Bosons minus respectively:

$$[\delta g_i, \delta g'_i] \pm = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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